

DIDACTIC CAPABILITIES OF E-LEARNING RESOURCES IN IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING NUCLEAR TECHNOLOGY IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS.

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Annotation: *This article provides feedback on the didactic capabilities of e-learning resources in improving the effectiveness of teaching nuclear technology.*

Keywords: *e-learning resource, virtual stand, animation, digitization, pedagogical tool.*

One of the main aspects of improving the educational system of our country is the modernization of the digitization of the educational process. "The digitization of the learning process is a system of combined methods, processes and software and technical means for the purpose of collecting, processing, storing, disseminating information and using Training" " [1]

With the introduction of digital technologies, the specifics of Education change, and the scope of the use of electronic education resources in the educational process increases. This serves as an important tool for improving the effectiveness of the educational and educational process of higher education institutions [2].

E-learning resources are a modern pedagogical software tool for increasing students' interest in science, obtaining independent education, the formation and development of their professional competence. Therefore, the development of new approaches to the introduction of electronic educational resources in higher educational institutions remains one of the pressing problems today. E-education with the help of resources, the professor-teacher focuses on the organization of active types of cognitive activity of students in nuclear technology, uses educational information not as a goal of teaching, but as a means of organizing the cognitive activity of teaching. In this, the student, in turn, together with the professor-teacher, is a subject of activity, and his personal development serves as one of the main educational goals. The use of interactive e-

learning resources in training organized in the field of nuclear technology, students [3]

For example, video rollers, virtual stands and animation effects serve as an important pedagogical tool when there is no opportunity to demonstrate processes and events related to the topic "radiation therapy" in nuclear technology. Interactive e-learning resources to improve the effectiveness of Teaching Nuclear Technology in higher educational institutions on the basis of the presented analytical data provide the following opportunities: increases student activity, motivation and interest in science; ease of Use, ability to model and predict the situation, complex impact on sensations, enhance audio-visual effects and develop Information, Research, search capabilities; combining with traditional sources of information Individual and differential of training.

In conclusion, the use of interactive e-learning resources in combination with innovative forms and methods of teaching to improve the quality of training of future teachers and doctors in higher educational institutions necessitates the improvement of menkhanism. The use of interactive e-learning resources is considered important in improving the effectiveness of teaching professional disciplines taught in the training of future physical teachers, in particular nuclear technology. This gave positive results when used in Samarkand State Medical University and Samarkand state medical universities, which used electron learning resources. This summary is No. AM-PZ-2019062031 "creation of multimedia textbooks for bachelors and masters in the disciplines "nuclear energy", "nuclear medicine and technology", "Radiation Medicine and technology".written in the framework of the innovative project named "" was eaten on the basis of the pedogogonic Assembly of materials

USED LITERATURE:

1. E.X Bozorov. E.J Ergashev. Oliy ta'lim muassaslarida "Rentgen diognostikasi" mavzusini o'qitishda interfaol usullardan foydalanish uslublari. O'zMU xabarlarі вестник нууз аста нууз мирзо улуфбек номідагі ўзбекистон миллий университети илмий журналі тошкент – 2022 yil 68-71 betlar

2. E.X Bozorov. E.J Ergashev. Yadro texnologiya fanlarini o'qitishda innovatsiyalar: ijodiy jamoa metodi Mutafakkir illmiy jurnali 2-son ISSN:2181-3310 №1 2- may Toshkent 2022 y 159-164 betla.

3. Прохорова М.П., Ваганова О.И. Участие преподавателей вуза в разработке открытых онлайн-курсов // Отечественная и зарубежная педагогика. 2019. Т. 1. № 5 (62). С. 90-103.

4. Кутепов М.М. Дидактические возможности интерактивных электронных образовательных ресурсов // Baltic Humanitarian Journal. 2020. Т. 9. № 3(32). - С. 128-130.

5. Андриенко О.А. Современные образовательные технологии: технология самопрезентации // Балканское научно обозрение. 2019. Т. 3. № 1 (3). С. 5